

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Investigating the Perceptions of Educational Stakeholders on the Introduction of Chinese as a foreign language in Zanzibar : Taking Mkoani District of Pemba as an Example

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Abstract

This paper aimed at probing the perception of education stakeholders on the introduction of the Chinese language in Zanzibar, the challenges, and its effects on Zanzibar culture. The study employed both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Questionnaires, focus group conversation, and interviews were used in data collection. A sample of 62 repliers was involved in the study including 20 students, 34 teachers, 6 head teachers, and 2 educational officers. The study employed stratified sampling and purposive sampling techniques in opting the samples. Purposive sampling was used to select the teachers, head teachers, and the educational officer while stratified sampling was used to sample the students. Interviews were conducted with head teachers and educational officers whereas focus group discussions and questionnaires were taken to students and teachers respectively. The data collected through the questionnaires were interpreted using software (SPSS) version 20; while information collected using interviews as well as focus group discussion was analysed qualitatively. The results were unambiguous as about 92.78% of respondents accepted the idea of introducing Chinese as a foreign language at secondary schools in Zanzibar. Meanwhile, the findings showed that the preface of the Chinese language would be faced with a myriad of challenges similar as a deficit of competent Chinese subject teachers, deficit of educational coffers, employing traditional style of tutoring and the final study revealed that the introduction of foreign language has little negative effects on the Zanzibar culture, in the meantime paper mentioned that the language literacy and culture has a great relation between. The study recommended that Chinese as a foreign language can be introduced at secondary schools in Zanzibar but the use of ultramodern tutoring style; frequent training of Chinese subject teachers and teaching Chinese subjects unhappy environment must be admired for better performance.

Keywords: Stakeholders; Educational Stakeholders; Foreign Language; Chinese Language

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1.Introduction

Nowadays understanding second languages is very essential. The famous language spoken includes English, French, and German. Currently, Chinese is well-known and commonly practiced as a foreign language by several inhabitants around the globe (Victoria 2021). The perception of native inhabitants on the introduction of a foreign language increased dramatically. At present, foreign languages happen to have great significance

among the people in different nations and they have started to learn foreign languages gradually. Understanding a second language is exceptionally valuable, in both aspects of economic and social matters. Proficiency in speaking a foreign language helps to influence a good relationship with other people. Many countries around the globe are progressively attracted to speaking two or more two languages because of the effect of globalization (Imam, 2005). Different countries such as Korea, Japan, Thailand,